

Preprint

Repercussions of Unbalanced Phases on the Performance of Induction Motors and the Financial Solvency of Companies

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Abstract: The study focuses on analyzing, through simulation, the effects caused by operating induction motors with unbalanced phases in industries. Thus, to achieve the goal mentioned, we chose a 30 HP motor as the sample, determining its electrical parameters using equations, we conducted electrical simulations through Simulink and thermal simulations using SolidWorks. While Simulink showed different values of power consumption based on imbalances levels, SolidWorks showed an increment in temperature based on consumed power. In the process we determined that the efficiency and operating expenditure changed based on the imbalance percentage. In conclusion, the results claim that power consumption, temperature and operating cost rate increase directly proportional to the imbalance value, negatively affecting machine efficiency and making an unexpected failure due to overheating more probable.

Keywords: induction motors; unbalanced phases; power consumption; efficiency; machine performance; overheating.

I. Introduction

The three - phase motor is the most popular machine in all industries, specifically when referring to AC motors, because their design and construction are simple and rugged. Furthermore, their low cost, high efficiency, good power factor, and low maintenance cost are useful advantages of this type of machine. Therefore, approximately 90% of the mechanical power used in the industry is provided by induction motors ¹. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), in 2022 electric motors and motor-driven systems represented around 70% of the electricity used by the industrial sector. For this reason, governments must implement standards to dictate efficiency levels for low-voltage AC motors ². However, in 2023 only 62 countries had standards for motors in industries, representing 57% of international energy consumption ³.

One of the components of an induction motor is the stator winding, which has a three-phase winding. The stator of a motor is wound for a specific number of poles, which is determined according to the requirements ¹. Moreover, it is important to highlight that each pole is placed at an equal distance and has the same number of wires turns, producing the same magnetic field strength. Each phase of the three-phase winding is delayed by 120° relative to the others, but being an identical image of the others ⁴. In other words, three identical coils are wound and placed within the stator to create a uniquely balanced three-phase winding ⁵.

In general terms, a motor is designed to have a symmetrical number of turns in each phase ⁴. When a 3-phase supply is applied to a stator, three currents flow through the stator winding, producing a magnetic field ¹. However, the phases become asymmetrical when a voltage imbalance occurs, causing poor performance of this machine ⁶. An unbalanced voltage is equivalent to removing turns from one phase and adding them to another phase, resulting in phase imbalances and magnetic field issues ⁴. Besides the poor conditions it can cause, this phenomenon also causes the degradation of the stator winding, leading to failure due to a constant increase in internal heat ⁶. An unbalanced voltage has the potential to produce, under certain conditions, an increase of 40% to 50% in the initial temperature. In addition, due to this overheating, there is a drastic reduction in the life expectancy of the induction motor ⁷. Specifically, while shorted turns result in winding failure, unbalanced phases increase stator losses and can result in circulating currents through the stator ⁸. In contrast, when the phenomenon of unbalanced voltage remains unattended, it can worsen and lead to total failure over time ⁹. As a result, a motor failure has the potential to cause lost production, delay activities, and upset customers of industries ¹⁰.

For monitoring the temperature increase, known as the measured differential temperature, it is necessary to use the thermography technique, which is a useful way to analyze this phenomenon. This method compares the temperature of components or machines in contrast to the ambient temperature, considering environmental and operating conditions. The technique provides enough information to determine thermal exceptions and serious problems ¹¹.

According to Oluseyi et al. ⁶, when the unbalanced voltage increases, the stator losses and the rotor losses increase proportionally, causing a decrease in motor efficiency as a result of this poor performance. Furthermore, considering rising energy costs and government policies that have promoted motor efficiency

over decades worldwide, this poor performance can impact companies' profits. In addition, when a motor experiences many failures, it drastically reduces the competitiveness of industries ¹⁰.

According to Kanwarjit ¹², when an induction motor experiences unbalanced phases, the current increases rapidly in one phase in contrast to the others. In addition, excessive overheating takes place and the efficiency drops considerably. The author claims that absence of unbalanced voltage in a system is almost impossible due to the random conditions of the electrical system itself. For this reason, the article suggests the use of computer simulation as a method to study the excessive heating of an induction motor during its operation with unbalanced phases.

According to Pillay and Hofmann ¹³, under normal conditions, the level of imbalance is too small to affect the motor's performance, unless the imbalance increases. However, when the motor operates near or beyond the 100% voltage consumption with an imbalance of 5%, it should not operate anymore. On the other hand, the author asserts that there are no significant derating differences when the machine works below the 5% threshold.

To determine the parameter values of a stator, it is necessary to perform tests on the induction motor. Moreover, among the several available tests, there are the No-Load Test and the DC Test for stator resistance. First of all, the No-Load Test is basically an evaluation of the motor's performance during its operation, in which the shaft spins freely without any load. On the other hand, the DC Test is mainly used to measure the stator resistance in each coil. During the test, a DC voltage is applied to the stator winding, where the current flows through the three-phase winding and the stator resistance is measured ¹⁴.

During the No-Load Test, the percentage of current flow can vary depending on the number of poles in the machine. Specifically, motors with 2 poles have a No-Load current flow ranging from 25% to 33% of the nominal current, while motors with 4 poles range from 33% to 40%, also motors with 6 poles range from 33% to 45%, while motors with 8 poles range from 33% to 65%, machines with 10 or more poles can experience a No-Load current flow ranging from 60% to 110% of the nominal current during testing. However, there are exceptions, which may have values outside of these guidelines, mainly motors with 10 poles or more ¹⁵.

According to Le Roux and Ngwenyama ¹⁶, the performance of the stator and rotor can be studied using dynamic and static simulations in Simulink, modeling an induction machine. Furthermore, when the machine is modeled in MATLAB - Simulink, the internal parameters of a motor can be estimated without needing any physical techniques. It is a fact that the algorithm used to simulate induction machines provides accurate information, with a deviation of no more than $\pm 2\%$ from the measured parameters.

The current study focuses on the analysis of a 30 HP induction motor to demonstrate the existence of poor performance when the motor works in unbalanced phases. Specifically, this study shows the impact on the motor's efficiency and internal heating due to an unbalanced winding in the machine. Furthermore, through computational simulation, changes in the machine's performance will be analyzed under normal operating conditions, in contrast to when the machine operates under unbalanced conditions.

To analyze changes in motor performance during operation, it is necessary to refer to the current standard. For this case, the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) 1415-2006 states that the allowable percentage of unbalanced voltage is less than 1%, and if the unbalance is higher than 5%, the machine should no longer operate ¹⁷.

II. Materials and Methods

First of all, the equipment and equations used in the current study are shown in the following sections, where we start by describing the motor implemented and continue by describing the equipment and software utilized.

2.1. Chosen Induction Motor

The AC motor selected (Figure 1a) is an asynchronous machine or induction motor from the WEG company, which has a rated power of 30 HP (22 kW), it is capable of operating at voltage levels of 220/380/440 volts with corresponding currents of 74.40/43.10/37.20 amperes at a frequency of 60 Hz. The nominal efficiency of the machine is 90.20%, its power factor ($\cos \varphi$) is 0.86, and its nominal speed is 1175 RPM. Finally, the machine was manufactured in 2001 and has a frame size of 200L, as can be seen in Figure 1b.

Figure 1. (a) 30 HP induction machine selected for the study. **(b)** Nameplate of the induction motor.

2.2. Equipment for performing the No-Load Test

The motor needs to be energized using a 3-phase supply that complies with the motor's energy requirements shown on its nameplate (Figure 1b). Therefore, any source of power capable of providing more than 440 volts and 37.20 amperes can be used. Specifically, it is necessary to use a 3-phase Auto-Transformer, capable of providing at least 30 HP (22 kW). Once we connect the supply to the induction motor, we need an instrument to measure voltage, current, and/or power in each phase of the motor that needs to be analyzed. The measuring instrument must be connected as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. No-Load Test Scheme Procedure (Source: Sahdev S. 1).

2.3. Instrument for performing the DC Test

There are several techniques to measure motor parameters and study its conditions over time. However, the current study focuses only on measuring the stator winding characteristics. For this reason, the instrument must be capable of performing the Motor Circuit Analysis Testing, which gives us phase-by-phase information about resistance, capacitance, inductance, and impedance ¹¹. Additionally, this type of test is a non-invasive fault detection technique that is useful to detect faults by analyzing motor conditions ¹⁸. Therefore, for the study, the

Baker DX 12 kV instrument was selected to gather the parameters of the 30 HP induction motor, as can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Instrument selected to gather the motor's parameters (Source: Megger Company ¹⁹).

2.4. Software for performing the simulation

When the gathering has been successful, it would be necessary to use MATLAB - Simulink to simulate the impact on the current flow input in the stator, which can be useful to visualize the current behavior during the start and normal operation of the motor. In addition, the implementation of SolidWorks - Thermal Simulation is required to study the heating behavior inside the stator, specifically in the winding, where the heating distribution needs to be analyzed.

2.5. Method for gathering the stator parameters

Once the testing has been completed using the Baker DX or another similar instrument to carry out the DC Test, the collected data must be used to obtain the required parameters for performing the simulation in Simulink, as shown in the equations in the following subsections.

2.5.1. Slip and poles number

When a 3-phase voltage is applied to the stator winding, current flows through each phase, producing a rotating magnetic field in the counterclockwise direction ¹⁴. Furthermore, to obtain this magnetic field speed (η_{sync}), it is necessary to use the following equation.

$$\eta_{sync} = \frac{120(f)}{N_p} \quad (1)$$

Where f is the supply frequency in Hz, N_p is the machine's poles number in rev/min (RPM).

Normally, equation (1) to obtain the magnetic field speed is commonly used to calculate the number of poles inside AC motors.

The slip is a way to describe the relative motion expressed in percentage units ¹⁴. Moreover, to obtain the slip (s) of the machine, it is necessary to gather the speed of the shaft transmissions.

$$s = \frac{\eta_{sync} - \eta_{shaft}}{\eta_{sync}} \quad (2)$$

2.5.2. Slip and poles number

To estimate the parameters of an induction machine, it is necessary to understand the equivalent circuit per phase, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Equivalent per-phase circuit with rotor and stator losses (Source: Chapman S. ¹⁴).

Where I_1 is the current that flows through the stator, R_2 is the stator resistance, X_1 is the stator reactance, I_M is the magnetizing current, X_M is the magnetizing reactance, R_C is the stator core losses, X_2 is the rotor reactance, R_2 is the rotor resistance, and I_{conv} is the rotor losses.

Despite the fact that the stator resistance is directly calculated during the DC Test, it is necessary to convert the measured value to the true resistance value, because the DC power supply is connected to two of the three terminals ¹⁴. Thus, equation (3) is used to find the true stator resistance when it is set in a star (WYE) connection.

$$R_1 = \frac{1}{2}(R_{DC}) \quad (3)$$

Despite the fact that it is possible to measure stator resistances during the DC Test, the reactance must be determined using different methods ¹⁴. Thus, the stator reactance can be found using equation (4), considering the supply frequency and the measured stator inductance ⁵.

$$X_1 = 2\pi(f_s)(L_1) \quad (4)$$

To determine the rotor reactance, it is necessary to use the supply frequency, knowing that $f_r = (s)(f_s)$, because the magnitude and frequency of the induced voltage in the rotor are directly proportional to the slip in the machine ¹⁴. Therefore, it is possible to obtain the rotor reactance using equation (5).

$$X_2 = 2\pi(f_r)(L_2) \quad (5)$$

However, when the machine undergoes a No-Load Test, the circuit changes considerably, as shown in Figure 5 ¹⁴. Furthermore, using this scheme makes the calculation of the magnetizing inductance between the rotor and stator easier than the previous one (Figure 4). Thus, when inductances are in parallel, it is necessary to apply the following relation $L_{eq} = (L_1)(L_2)/(L_1 + L_2)$. However, when inductances are in series, they must be summed or added together ¹. Applying this basic knowledge of electromagnetism, it is possible to find the total inductance in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Equivalent per-phase circuit during No-Load Test (Source: Chapman S. ¹⁴).

The following equation can be used to find the total inductance of the first scheme (Figure 4).

$$L_T = L_1 + \frac{(L_2)(L_M)}{(L_2 + L_M)} \quad (6)$$

To determine mutual inductance (L_M), it is necessary to obtain the magnetization reactance by applying variables from the No-Load Test and using equation (7), as shown below.

$$X_M = \frac{V_{NL}}{(I_{NL}) \sin \varphi} \quad (7)$$

Where V_{NL} is the applied no-load test voltage and I_{NL} is the current consumed by the machine during the test.

2.5.3. Rotor resistance

Despite the fact that no data was collected from the test named "Locked-Rotor Test", we can use its theory and equations to determine the rotor resistance (R_2), using certain parameters from the motor's datasheet. In general terms, the Locked-Rotor Test is performed using a frequency of 25% or less than the rated frequency. Additionally, the impedance can be calculated using equation (8), following below ¹⁴.

$$Z_{LR} = R_{LR} + jX'_{LR} \quad (8)$$

Where R_{LR} is the total resistance during the test and X'_{LR} is the total reactance at the test frequency.

The impedance value in a motor under Locked-Rotor test conditions, can be calculated using the voltage and the current consumed ¹⁴.

$$Z_{LR} = \frac{V_L}{\sqrt{3}(I_L)} \quad (9)$$

The Locked-Rotor reactance is equal to the sum of the stator and rotor reactance at the test frequency ¹⁴.

$$X'_{LR} = X'_1 + X'_2 \quad (10)$$

According to Chapman ¹⁴, over the years, experience has shown us that there are certain proportions between the rotor and stator reactance based on the motor's design. However, in practice, there are cases that could break this relationship. To make this easier, it is necessary to use this relationship between X'_1 and X'_2 , using the following table.

Table 1. Relationship between the stator and rotor reactance according to the Locked-Rotor reactance value.

Rotor Design	X_1	X_2
Wound rotor	$0.50X_{LR}$	$0.50X_{LR}$
Design A	$0.50X_{LR}$	$0.50X_{LR}$
Design B	$0.40X_{LR}$	$0.60X_{LR}$
Design C	$0.30X_{LR}$	$0.70X_{LR}$
Design D	$0.50X_{LR}$	$0.50X_{LR}$

¹⁴ Extracted from Chapman, S.

Considering that the reactance is directly proportional to the frequency, it is possible to find the total reactance at the normal operating frequency X_{LR} ¹⁴.

$$X_{LR} = \left(\frac{f_{rated}}{f_{test}} \right) X'_{LR} = X_1 + X_2 \quad (11)$$

Finally, we can obtain the rotor resistance X_2 , using the stator resistance from the DC test and locked-rotor resistance in equation (12).

$$R_{LR} = R_1 + R_2 \quad (12)$$

2.5.4. Machine Efficiency

It is a common concept and is important to carry out the current study. In a few words, efficiency is a relation between output power and input power ⁵. Generally, output power increases directly proportional to shaft speed, while electrical consumption remains constant; efficiency increases according to speed ²⁰.

$$X_{LR} = \left(\frac{P_{out}}{P_{input}} \right) \quad (13)$$

Where P_{input} is the electrical power from the supply to the stator winding and P_{out} is the mechanical power in the motor's shaft transmission.

Power, in simple terms, is the rate of how much work is done or the work per unit of time, generally measured in joules per second (watts). When we refer to the electrical power input in induction motors, the power is given by the input voltage and current, as shown below ¹⁴.

$$P_{input} = \sqrt{3}(V_L)(I_L)(\cos \varphi) \quad (14)$$

Where V_L is the line input voltage, I_L is the line input current, and $\cos \varphi$ is the power factor.

According to the IEA, the price of energy was established at USD 10/MBtu on the European continent ³. Thus, the power consumption would be represented in terms of costs as USD 0.0341/kW, making this rate important to determine the annual energy losses in monetary terms.

2.5.5. Number of turns in a winding

The inductance always depends on the physical dimensions of the coil and the permeability of the material that shaped it. Therefore, the inductance value in a toroidal winding depends on its own measurement ⁵.

$$L_{ls} = \frac{\mu}{2\pi}(N^2)(h)(\ln b/a) \quad (15)$$

Where, μ is the air permeability, N is the turns in the coil, h is the height of the core, b is the total radius of the core, and a is the air radius inside the core.

Generally, μ quantifies the magnetic properties of the vacuum, also called "free space", but for engineering purposes, the air permeability is equal to the vacuum permeability, both of them are equal to $4\pi \times 10^{-7}$ H/m ²⁰.

III. Results

First of all, after the DC test using the Baker DX, it is necessary to summarize the collected data, which show the characteristics of the induction motor.

3.1. Data collected from the conducted tests

Table 2. Data collected from using the Baker DX 12kV equipment.

Variable	1-2	2-3	3-1	Average
R_{DC} (m Ω)	280.5062	279.3642	280.2353	280.0352
f_{tested} (Hz)	60	60	60	60
Z_{DC} (m Ω)	1.665	1.661	1.664	1.663
ϕ ($^{\circ}$)	82.40	82.40	82.20	82.40
L_{DC} (mH)	4.377	4.368	4.375	4.373

As can be seen in Table 2, the machine does not have unbalanced phases because each phase has the same value with respect to the others. Therefore, if we measure the current, voltage, or power consumption during the No-Load Test, the results must corroborate the absence of unbalanced phases. The results of the No-Load Test are summarized in the following table.

Table 3. Data collected from the No-Load Test.

Variable	1-2	2-3	3-1	Average
I_{AC} (A)	17.80	17.50	18.10	17.80
V_{AC} (A)	440.50	440.70	441.40	440.80
f_{AC} (Hz)	60	60	60	60

3.2. Motor parameters calculation

Applying equation (7) and using the data from Table 3, we can obtain the magnetizing reactance of our machine, assuming that there are no losses in the motor due to friction or winding.

$$X_M = \frac{440.80 V}{(17.80 A) \sin 63.26^\circ} = 27.73 \Omega$$

The angle (φ) was extracted from the power curve of the motor's datasheet, which is necessary to determine all motor parameters.

Applying equation (4), we can determine the mutual inductance of the motor, as shown below.

$$27.73 \Omega = 2\pi(60 \text{ Hz})(L_m)$$

$$L_m = 0.074 \text{ H}$$

From Table 2, we can determine the stator resistance and the leakage inductance. Firstly, it is necessary to apply equation (3) to find the true value of the stator resistance when it is connected in a star configuration.

$$R_1 = \frac{1}{2} (280.0352 \text{ m}\Omega) = 0.14 \Omega$$

Using the same equation, we can obtain the true inductance measured in the motor, as shown below.

$$L_T = \frac{1}{2} (4.373 \text{ mH}) = 0.002187 \text{ H}$$

Now, applying equation (6), it is possible to find the stator leakage inductance, highlighting that during the DC Test, the rotor was removed from the motor. Therefore, the rotor leakage inductance is equal to zero, which results in the following results.

$$L_{lr} = 0 \quad (\text{rotor removed from the motor})$$

$$L_T = L_{ls} + \frac{(L_{lr})(L_M)}{(L_{lr} + L_M)}$$

$$L_{ls} = L_T = 0.002187 \text{ H}$$

Finally, applying the properties and theories of the Locked-Rotor Test, we can find the missing rotor resistance. Firstly, we need to apply equation (7) to obtain the leakage rotor reactance, assuming that the chosen motor was manufactured using a rotor design A or D from the Table 1.

$$X_{LR} = \left(\frac{f_{rated}}{f_{test}} \right) X'_{LR} = X_1 + X_2$$

The variable X_1 is equal to X_2 and we get the stator leakage inductance L_{ls} from the DC Test, the previous equation can be solved applying equation (4), as shown below (assuming that the Locked-Rotor test was carried out at 15% of the rated frequency, according to theory).

$$X_1 = X_2 = 2\pi(60 \text{ Hz})(0.002187 \text{ H}) = 0.8245 \Omega$$

$$(2)(0.8245 \Omega) = \left(\frac{60 \text{ Hz}}{(0.15)(60 \text{ Hz})} \right) X'_{LR}$$

$$X'_{LR} = 0.2474 \Omega$$

Using equation (8) and equation (9), it is possible to find the rotor resistance, remembering that according to equation (72), the Locked-Rotor resistance (R_{LR}) is equal to $R_1 + R_2$.

$$(Z_{LR})^2 = (R_{LR})^2 + (X'_{LR})^2$$

$$\left(\frac{V_L}{\sqrt{3}(I_L)} \right)^2 = (R_1 + R_2)^2 + (X'_{LR})^2$$

According to the motor's datasheet, there is a factor used to obtain the Locked-Rotor current and voltage, which shows a value of 4.30 times the nominal current.

$$\left(\frac{(460/4.30)}{\sqrt{3}(37.10)(4.30)} \right)^2 = (0.14 \Omega + R_2)^2 + (0.2474 \Omega)^2$$

$$(R_2)^2 + 0.28R_2 + 0.0196 + 0.0612 - 0.150 = 0$$

$$R_2 = 0.16 \Omega$$

3.3. Motor current consumption simulation using Simulink

Now, it is necessary to summarize all results to conduct the simulation in Simulink, as is shown below.

Table 4. Collected data to conduct the first simulation in Simulink.

Parameter	Value	Simulink Block
Voltage	440 V	AC Voltage Sources
Torque	178.80 N.m	Constant
Slip	0.208	
Poles pairs	3	
Stator Resistance	0.14 Ω	
Stator Leakage Inductance	0.002187 H	Asynchronous Machine
Rotor Resistance	0.16 Ω	
Rotor Leakage Inductance	0.002187 H	
Mutual Inductance	0.0712 H	

The variables shown in Table 4 must be inserted into a Simulink model, following a logical algorithm that allows us to obtain the stator current consumed by each phase of the three-phase coil. Therefore, the model used for the simulation is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Simulink model used to simulate the current consumption of each phase in the motor.

Once we inserted the data from Table 4, we can visualize the current consumption of each phase from the machine's start-up to its normal operation. Therefore, as can be seen in Figure 7, the consumption of each phase seems very symmetrical, approximating the rated current from the nameplate in Figure 1.

Figure 7. First simulation of current consumption in each phase using Simulink.

To observe how an unbalanced phase would affect motor performance and efficiency, it is necessary to create an imbalance in one of the three phases, following the limit mentioned in the IEEE 1415 standard. Therefore, the AC Voltage Source B (Phase 2) of the Asynchronous Machine is going to be imbalanced by +2.00% compared to the others. As can be seen in Figure 8, one phase has lower consumption than the others.

Figure 8. Second simulation of current consumption with one phase operating at 449.62 volts.

Now, it is necessary to simulate one unbalanced phase with a variation of +5.00% in the same phase, a value that the IEEE 1415 normative states that the motor should not operate. As can be seen in Figure 9, all phases consume different values of amperes.

Figure 9. Third simulation of current consumption with one phase operating at 462.84 volts.

Finally, as a last test, we can simulate the motor under a +10.00% voltage imbalance in the same phase to analyze how this affects current consumption in the stator. Thus, as can be seen in Figure 10, the consumption is higher than before, as we expected it to be.

Figure 10. Fourth simulation of current consumption with one phase operating at 484.88 volts.

Collecting all values from each result, we can calculate the consumed power and efficiency for each case. As shown in Table 5, once the unbalanced phase (Phase 2) increases, the power consumption also rises.

Table 5. Collected data to conduct the first simulation in Simulink.

Source	(%) Unbalanced voltage	Resulting current (A)	Power consumed (kW)	Efficiency (%)
Nameplate	0.00%	37.20	24.38	90.20
Simulation 1	0.00%	38.73	25.38	86.75
Simulation 2	2.00%	39.67	26.57	82.80
Simulation 3	5.00%	40.60	27.99	78.60
Simulation 4	10.00%	42.99	31.05	70.85

3.4. Motor temperature simulation using SolidWorks

To analyze the impact of the power consumption for each current consumption value on the motor, we need to insert each power flux into a simulation software such as SolidWorks. Firstly, we need to design each component of the motor. Therefore, as can be seen below, the chosen motor is shown in Figure 11, which will be simulated using thermal simulation.

Figure 11. Chosen motor designed in SolidWorks - Exploded view.

Applying equation (15), we can obtain the number of turns (N) that has the motor winding. However, during thermal simulation, it is necessary to simplify the model to avoid delays in the simulation process performed by the software.

$$N = \sqrt{\frac{2\pi(L)}{(\mu_o)(h)(\ln b/a)}} = 311.27 \text{ turns}$$

$$N_{phase} = \frac{312}{72} = 4.32 \text{ turns/slot}$$

$$N_T = \left(4.32 \frac{\text{turns}}{\text{slot}}\right) (3 \text{ phases}) \approx 13 \text{ turns/slot}$$

As shown in Figure 12, the simplification of the model is an important step in conducting an easier simulation, which in this case the winding is simplified by assuming an entire conductor or copper wire, which supposes to contain the number of wires of the real winding that pass through each stator slot. Therefore, because each slot must have 13 copper wires, the unique conductor must have a maximum diameter of 12 mm, as can be seen in Figure 12. However, when we use a mathematical approach, the exact diameter of the unique wire is 10.82 mm, because it occupies the same area as the 13 copper wires in each slot, as can be seen below.

Figure 12. Winding simplification to start the thermal simulation.

Using the previously mentioned measurement, the winding must be designed to apply the thermal simulation in SolidWorks. Before that, we need to set up the simulation parameters that will interact with the motor during its operation. Thus, the values shown in Table 6, must be inserted into the simulator before performing the thermal simulation.

Table 6. Parameters used in the thermal simulation

Variable	Value	Note
Material	Copper	SolidWorks' library
Air convection coefficient	300 W/m ² . °K	Forced Convection
Ambient temperature	293° K	N/A

Heat power

Inserted by User (W)

According to the
method

To start the simulation, we need to set up each power consumption obtained previously in the simulator. Beginning with the No-Load Test power consumption, follows for nameplate power consumption, and ending with the last simulation done by Simulink. Therefore, as can be seen in Figure 13, the first image represents the increase in temperature as a result of the power consumption during the No-Load Test and the second image represents the electrical input power according to the nameplate.

Figure 13. (a) Coil temperature during No-Load Test at 11.69 kW. **(b)** Coil temperature at the nameplate power of 24.38.

Now, the following simulations show the temperature increment or heat gained because of the percentage of unbalanced phases. As shown in Figure 14a, when there are no unbalanced phases, the temperature is close to the resulting temperature according to the power consumption of the nameplate (Figure 13b). However, while the percentage of unbalanced phases increases, the temperature rises directly proportional.

Figure 14. Winding temperature at different input electrical power values. **(a)** Coil operating at 25.38 kW. **(b)** Coil operating at 26.57 kW. **(c)** Coil operating at 27.99 kW. **(d)** Coil operating at 31.05 kW.

3.5. Motor performance based on unbalanced phases

As shown in Table 7, while the unbalanced phase increases, the temperature and the spending rate also experience an increase. The table shows information about the performance of the motor in unbalanced operation, but assumes that it provides a constant output mechanical energy during 24 hours and 365 days of the year.

Table 7. Spending rate and temperature increment based on the unbalanced phases.

Source	Power consumed (kW)	Cost Rate (USD/year)	Avoidable spending (USD/year)	Temperature Increment (°C)
No-Load Test	11.69	N/A	0.00	N/A
Nameplate	24.38	7282.70	0.00	68.23
Simulation 1	25.38	7581.41	N/A	73.62
Simulation 2	26.57	7936.88	654.18	79.99
Simulation 3	27.99	8361.06	1078.36	87.64
Simulation 4	31.05	9275.13	1992.43	104.08

IV. Discussion

The first simulation in Simulink (Figure 7) must be aligned with the current consumption shown on the machine nameplate. However, while the nameplate indicates a line current equal to 37.20 amperes, the simulation gave us a line current equal to an average of 38.70 amperes, making a percentage deviation of approximately +4.00%, greater than the deviation mentioned by Le Roux and Ngwenyama in their publication ¹⁶. Nevertheless, the difference is small enough to be ignored and used as a reference for the increase in current consumption in the following simulations. Furthermore, when the consumed power is

introduced into SolidWorks (Figure 14a), the thermal simulation claims a maximum temperature increment of 156.30°C in the load region (P_1), operating approximately at the threshold insulation temperature according to the type of insulation mentioned by the nameplate. In contrast, the ventilation region (P_2) shows a lower temperature than (P_1), measuring 99.53°C , because the fan is located at that point, removing the heating from the coil to the surrounding environment. The maximum differential temperature for this case is 73.62°C , compared to the No-Load operating temperature, which makes sense because the machine works under full load conditions.

The second simulation of current consumption (Figure 8) shows that Phase 2 consumed 39.67 amperes, which was caused by an overconsumption of voltage in that phase, consuming 8.82 volts more than other phases at 440 volts. Therefore, this overconsumption of voltage in Phase 2 produces an imbalanced current consumption between all phases of the motor. Moreover, when power consumption is introduced in SolidWorks (Figure 14b), the resulting thermal simulation is equal to 162.67°C in (P_1) and 103.25°C in (P_2), representing a maximum temperature increase of 6.37°C compared to the first simulation. The maximum differential temperature is 79.99°C with the No-Load operation temperature.

The third simulation (Figure 9) shows a greater imbalance of current consumption, because the voltage in Phase 2 consumes 22.04 volts more than in other phases. Therefore, Phase 2 experiences a current line of 40.595 amperes. In addition, when the power value is introduced in the thermal simulator (Figure 14c), the temperature increases to 170.32°C in (P_1) and 107.72°C in (P_2), resulting in a maximum difference of 14.02°C . The maximum differential temperature is 87.64°C with the No-Load operation temperature.

The last simulation in Simulink (Figure 10) shows a greater perturbation in the motor consumption lines, Phase 3 has a less considerably consumed current than Phase 2 and Phase 1. When Phase 2 consumes 44.08 volts more than all phases, the motor not only experiences a current equal to 42.9893 amperes in Phase 2, it also experiences a huge disruption between phases during the performance. Furthermore, when the consumption is inserted into the thermal simulator (Figure 14d), the temperature increases to 186.76°C in (P_1) and 117.32°C in (P_2). Finally, for this simulation, the maximum differential temperature is 104.08°C with the No-Load operation temperature.

As shown in Table 5, the unnecessary power loss begins at 2.00% of the unbalanced voltage. Although the efficiency decreases slightly compared to the symmetrical phase simulation, it can be worse when the imbalance rises. As can be seen, power loss increases and efficiency decreases beyond 2.00% imbalances, creating a "derating" phenomenon in the machine, which is directly proportional to the percentage of unbalanced phase. This result aligns with the claim reported by Oluseyi et al. ⁶, where it suggests that losses increase proportionally when a motor experiences an imbalance condition, causing the decrease in efficiency. Furthermore, the result aligns according to the Kanwarjit publication ¹², mentioning that the current increases when the imbalance condition occurs, the machine experiences overheating, and the efficiency drops in the process. In addition, the publication of Pillay and Hofmann ¹³ suggests that when the motor starts near or beyond 5.00% under full load conditions, the machines should no longer operate because the imbalance significantly affects motor performance. This recommendation makes sense when we look at Table 5, the machine experiences a power consumption considerably greater than when operating under symmetrical conditions.

As shown in Table 7, as the unbalanced phase increases, the avoidable expenditure and the temperature difference also increase. However, the most important result is the awareness that as the imbalance percentage rises, so does the probability of failure due to the increasing overheating within the machine. This is because NASA publication ¹¹ indicates that when the temperature difference is greater than 10°, the machine needs to be repaired at the convenience or company's availability, but when the difference exceeds 80°, the machine must be repaired immediately. Therefore, as can be seen in Table 7, during an imbalance below or equal to 5.00%, the machine must be fixed according to the availability of the company's schedule, but when the imbalance exceeds 5.00%, the machine must be repaired as soon as possible. This recommendation is also mentioned in the IEEE 1415 standard ¹⁷, when the machine exceeds an imbalance 5.00%, it must not be in operation anymore because, beyond that level, the motor experiences a derating of the power and dangerous overheating.

For future research, it is highly recommended to use physical devices to measure the increase in power consumption instead of using simulators. Due to the uncertainty margin of the simulator and the possible inaccuracy results during the simulation processing, it is better to implement devices such as the

Wattmeter to directly measure the power and thermography to measure the overheat gained in the motor during the performance.

V. Conclusions

This study was aimed to analyze the consequences in motor performance under the condition of unbalanced phases. The Simulink results showed that current consumption increases as the percentage of imbalance rises, decreasing the efficiency in the process. Continually, the thermal simulation in SolidWorks showed that as a consequence of current increment, the internal temperature of the motor increases directly proportionally. Both simulators corroborate the claims provided by international standards and scientific papers, which mention that the motors have a poor performance when they work under higher imbalanced conditions. Therefore, when a company tends to operate with unbalanced motors, is a big mistake, because the cost rate of those machines increases considerably based of the imbalance percentage. In addition, the energy efficiency of companies decreases when they choose to continue using these machines instead of changing or repairing them. Therefore, in conclusion, it is a better choice to avoid motor imbalances beyond 5%, because the expenditure is high enough to cause financial losses for any company. Besides the loss of efficiency mentioned, an imbalance beyond that threshold could cause additional troubles for any company, and the differential temperature increases the probability of an unexpected failure in the machine, leading to further monetary losses that negatively affect the financial solvency of any business.

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